

ADAPTATION TO FLOODING WITHIN THE CITY BLOCK SCALE

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ABSTRACT. This paper is concerned with some central aspects and implications of flooding in urban environments, and it specifically focuses on a certain typology of flooding—surface water flooding—resulting from excess of surface water runoff as it occurs in London. In particular, the paper considers some of the main alternative strategies that can be used to reduce the risk of surface water flooding and pays specific attention to the benefits of SUDS. The suitability of SUDS in the urban context is tested through an approach focusing on the city block scale. Accordingly, quantitative simulation and critical discussion will be used to compare adaptive strategies of two types of city blocks in London: a typical Georgian block and a Modernist block. On this basis, the claim will be defended that the Modernist block can be better adapted not only to cope with its own surface water runoff but also to compensate as ‘active’ catchments for other parts of the city.

Keywords: Adaptation to Climate Change, City block, Surface Water Flooding, Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS), Measuring Resilience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent years flooding has become a major and (increasingly) chronic source of concern in the UK. London is no exception: while it is considered well protected against some types of flooding (such as tidal flooding) London is quite vulnerable to kinds of flooding that have other sources (such as fluvial flooding and, especially, surface water flooding). [8] Notably, the consequences, if not the likelihood, of flooding in London are potentially more serious than elsewhere in the UK because (a) London is heavily urbanised, (b) 15% of the city’s surface area lies on the floodplains of London river, and (c) in London more than 800,000 properties lie at risk of surface water flooding. [8]

In order to contextualise this problem and its impact on urban environments, by building on the existing literature concerning flooding this paper intends to contribute not only to better understand the overall phenomenon of flooding but also to highlight the different typologies of flooding and their interconnections. In this context, it will be shown that surface water runoff occupies a special position in the study and management of flooding, since it does not only causes a specific type of flooding—namely, surface water flooding—but also contributes to exacerbate, and increases the risk of, types of flooding that have their primary source elsewhere.

In addition, the paper identifies and critically assesses some of the main alternative strategies that can be used to reduce the risk of flooding originating in surface water runoff in London. In this process, the focus will be on the city block, and specifically on two specific city blocks located in London that present a radically different structure (both under the morphological and organisational point of view): a Georgian block in Bloomsbury and a Modernist block in Bethnal Green. By evaluating the impact of certain strategies for dealing with flooding on such diverse contexts, it will be established which general strategy is most adequate to reduce the risk of surface water flooding in London—strategy that, to anticipate the main

conclusions, can be concisely summarised as consisting in recommending an increased use of green roofs, planting and permeable surfaces in the city as well as highlighting the importance of the awareness that the Modern block provides optimal opportunities of adaptation, to the effect that it can compensate for other less adaptive city blocks (such as the Georgian block).

2. METHODS

This paper relies on three basic methods to address the main topic it is concerned with.

- I. Firstly, this paper has benefited from an extensive review of the literature devoted to flooding in general and surface water flooding in particular. The bulk of the literature considered in this work consists in the recent documentations, mostly published after the 2004 and 2007 episodes of flooding in the UK. The critical engagement with this literature enabled me to reconstruct the overall context—risk of flooding and connected requirement of re-adapting the city—in which this work can be located. The desk research carried out was also meant to clarify the relationships between different kinds of flooding affecting London and appreciate the importance of surface water flooding (which is not just an independent typology of flooding but also a major con-cause of other kinds of flooding experienced in London). Moreover, the literature review was meant to elucidate which phenomenon is ultimately the source of surface water runoff and which methods can be used to reduce the risk of its occurrence.
- II. With this general context reconstructed, I have critically analysed the strategies that can be used to tackle the challenges posed by the increased risk of surface water flooding, namely to reduce the surface water runoff. By doing this it has been single out a number of possible devices that can be used to cope with excess of surface water runoff. A comparative assessment within different devices was then performed with the aim to, first, single out two different strategies that have been suggested as possible means to reduce the risk of surface water runoff and, secondly, to assess those strategies by so identifying which device(s) is (or are) the most suitable one(s) in terms of costs and benefits (i.e. cost, maintenance, land-take, peak flow reduction and volume reduction) and in terms of extra benefits (i.e. pollution reduction, landscape/wildlife/amenity benefit).
- III. Finally, an analysis of the case study city blocks has been carried out. The analysis was justified by the purpose of showing that city blocks that present a different structure and are oriented to a different ideology—the Georgian block paradigmatically typified by Bloomsbury and the Modernist city block exemplified by Bethnal Green—call for different strategies of adaptation when they face the challenge posed by an increased risk of surface water flooding. ¹ In this context, it is been performed a simulation of the city block—which can be qualified as a quantitative method—by means of which I have established how much amount of surface water runoff can be retained within each of the city blocks under review to alleviate the existing drainage system in London. This city block simulation is aimed at assessing two SUDS-based strategies that can be followed in order to reduce the surface water runoff (hence, to enhance their permeable degree), and it is been performed through the following steps:
 - a. On first place, it was necessary to establish the amount of rainfall that affect each relevant city block. In order to do so I have hypothesised that future years will see

¹ In this context, it may be worthwhile to emphasise that neither Bloomsbury nor Bethnal Green are presently considered at risk of tidal or fluvial flooding but instead they both present a consistent ad spread risk of surface water flooding. [4] This makes them, in my view, ideal test cases to study, free from any practical urgency or concern, surface water flooding in London and identify and criticise the available solutions.

an increase of winter rainfall by 20%, as stated in the key findings contained in the UK Climate Projections. Since the data provided by the UK Climate Projections are relative to specific years and emission scenarios, some parameters have been fixed for the purpose of this study. The study will, then, be specifically referred to the projection taken to hold in London “under medium emissions, the central estimate of change in winter mean precipitation is 19%; it is very unlikely to be less than 3% and is very unlikely to be more than 44%”. [22]

- b. Then, it has been simulated an increase of permeability within the two relevant city blocks. Through this simulation, I will be able to evaluate the efficiency and feasibility that the proposed devices (green roofs and pervious surfaces) have in reducing the surface water runoff, when they are contextualised in Bloomsbury and Bethnal Green. The proposed simulation required one to calculate the area of all the available surfaces within each city block (such as roofs, pavements, backyards, etc.). This was followed by a simple calculation to sort out the degree of permeability² of the different materials to which the relevant city blocks are made of; this way one was able to calculate the percentage of permeability of each city block. This result was then compared with the value of permeability (which was expected to be higher) of the same area after its surface-materials were substituted by green roofs and pervious surfaces.
- c. Finally, by building on the results achieved in the previous steps, I had embarked into a critical discussion of the advantages and disadvantages in using green roofs and pervious surfaces to cope with surface water runoff in London.

3. THE RISK OF FLOODING

It has been estimated that over 5% of the people in England, some of whom residing in major cities such as York and London, live lower than 5 metres above sea level and so are at risk of being affected by flooding at some stage of their lives. [7] Significantly, the likelihood of flooding is projected to increase in the coming decades. In fact, a range of factors influences future flood risk. They include, among others, climate change and modifications in the use of land associated with urban growth. Of these two major factors climate change is likely to have the greater impact, as it is expected to increase both the probability of flooding and the consequences of flooding.³ [19]

Whilst it is impossible to predict exactly how climate change will affect the risk of flooding, the Thames Catchments Flood Management Plan (CFMP) has established key trends: (a) milder and wetter winters are likely to result in an increase of peak river flows up to 20%, meaning not only that flooding will happen more frequently, but also that large scale severe flooding are to be expected; (b) more frequent and intense storms, of short duration, are probable (especially in summer), which will produce more widespread and regular *flash flooding* caused by overwhelmed drainage systems as well as river flooding. [19]

The Environment Agency [19] **Error! Reference source not found.** identifies six distinct potential sources of flooding. They are (1) river flooding, (2) coastal flooding (or tidal flooding), (3) sewer flooding, (4) groundwater flooding, (5) reservoir flooding, and (6) surface water flooding. As the London Regional Flood Risk Appraisal (RFRA) [6] attests, only some of them (namely, river flooding, coastal flooding, sewer flooding, ground flooding

² For indexes of permeability, I direct the reader to Ritchie and Randall. [13]

³ In this context, one may want to take account of the fact that using a broad scale modelling strategy, the CFMP have estimated that the number of properties at a 1% risk of flooding from rivers in the Thames area will increase by approximately 20%, as a result of climate change.

and surface water flooding) concern London, though. In what follows I confine myself to consider one of them: surface water flooding.

Surface water flooding occurs when heavy rainfall overwhelms the drainage capacity of the local area and begins to form puddles and pools on the ground. This phenomenon is, within limits, far from exceptional. However, particularly violent storms may have the effect to completely overcome an area’s drainage system by so causing a local occurrence of flooding. [20] Because of its source (surface water runoff) surface water flooding is particularly likely as well as problematic where urban development is dense and the roof areas are large. As it is the case with fluvial flooding, the risk of surface water flooding is also affected by climate change, especially in consideration to the fact that climate change means, among other things, that the intensity and frequency of storms are likely to increase in the future. [21] As a result, both likelihood and consequences of surface water flooding are expected to increase. [18] This is why the Greater London Authority (GLA) regards surface water flooding as one of the most serious challenges that London will have to face in the near future. [20]

By its very nature, surface water flooding can occur very rapidly, affect only some areas in a neighbourhood, and tend to dissipate quickly. All these factors make occurrence of surface water flooding hard to predict. Related, since we lack a comprehensive system for recording surface water flooding, it is difficult to identify the areas in London that are particularly vulnerable to surface water flooding. [6] In order to reduce the risk of surface water flooding The London Plan [9] puts forward a number of different suggestions. Two of them stand out. For one thing, the London Plan recommends the introduction of sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS). SUDS have the potential to ensure a reduction of surface water runoff, since they can diminish the overall amount of rainfall being discharged into the pipe-based drainage system. In addition, the London Plan [9] specifically recommends the inclusion of green roofs in new urban developments. In this context, it is important to emphasise, however, that the recommendation is not compulsory. This choice is highly objectionable, since it significantly limits the practical efficacy of the suggested measure even in new developments (which anyway constitute a small portion of the overall London’s area).

Before proceeding, it should be noticed, however, that there are more that just one possible interaction between the different kinds of flooding.⁴ More specifically, as the interpretative diagram in fig. 1 shows, surface water flooding is the ultimate cause of most other types of flooding in London. This is one of the main reasons why coping with surface water flooding should be considered an essential step of any preventive or adaptive strategy in relation to flooding in general in London.

FIGURE 1. Relationship between types of flooding: surface water flooding is con-cause of other kinds of flooding (author’s own).

⁴ The different interactions between the various types of flooding have been discussed for instance in the London Regional Flood Risk Appraisal [6], to which I direct the reader for a comprehensive overview.

It is this belief—especially when combined with the awareness of the fact that tidal flooding has received much attention (think of the implementation of Thames barrier project) whereas surface water flooding is still understudied [6]—that provides the stronger justification to the choice of exploring, in this paper, some possible strategies for tackling specifically surface water flooding, which should then be regarded as the common source of most types of flooding in London.

4. SURFACE WATER FLOODING

In order to reduce the risk of surface water flooding it is necessary to reduce the surface water runoff. In order to cope with the problem of surface water runoff a number of strategies and devices have traditionally been designed and made used of. Not all of them, however, have proved to be effective, sustainable and feasible. Moreover, design for rainfall in the UK is difficult, since the defined hydrological conditions central to runoff-estimation are variable. [3] In addition, the picture is complicated and made less manageable by (a) the increased incurrence of flooding, (b) the increased urbanization with consequent increased runoff⁵; (c) the increased runoff due to the increase of imperviousness; (d) climate change. [3] These four factors are mutually related: for instance, increased urbanization (b) is a serious threat, especially in London, where urban developments have reduced the permeability of the land surface (c) more and more. Consequently, the amount of water that can infiltrate into the ground has been significantly reduced (see fig. 2). [17] Importantly, as shown in fig. 3, this tendency is unlikely to decrease, since urban developments are expected to continue.⁶

FIGURE 2. London’s development from middle Ages till today. [1]

FIGURE 3. London’s population 1971-2031. [9]

FIGURE 4. London climate projections. Maps: Change in winter mean precipitation (%). [21]

⁵ In 1998, urbanised areas occupied about 8% of England. By contrast, it is predicted that by 2016 urbanised areas will rise to 11.9%. [2]

⁶ The Greater London Authority has foreseen a 10% growing population by 2026, leading to a change in household by 16%, meaning an increase of one person per household. [9]

Finally, potential climate change (d) represents the emerging challenge for urban drainage systems. Global warming caused by the concentration of greenhouse gasses, in particular, translates into an increase of global-average surface and a rise of temperature. [3] As shown in fig. 4, this trend is expected to also lead to an increase of annual precipitations by 10% by 2080 (20% of which is projected to consist in winter precipitations). [21] In order to cope with potential climate change it would be necessary to either upgrade the existing sewer system or to increase the use of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS). Since upgrading the existing sewer network is far from a costless and easily viable option, it is arguable that the most practicable solution consists in making a more extensive use of SUDS. [3] In fact, just by reducing the amount of water entering municipal sewers through the use of SUDS, less wastewater will need treatment in sewage plants by so relieving the overall urban drainage system. [13]

There are two methods designated to cope with the surface water runoff: (a) traditional pipe-based systems and (b) non pipe-based systems (SUDS). Traditional systems used to deal with flooding consists in a system of underground pipe-based systems (a) that are designed to prevent flooding locally by conveying the water as quickly as possible. [17] They convey stormwater from inlet points (such as road gullies and roofs downpipes) to a discharge point by a series of pipes. [3] The design of pipe-based systems is, as Butler and Davis [3] observe, complex. For, the design of a drainage system must account for the fact that the magnitude and frequency of rainfall is unpredictable and can hardly be accurately known in advance. SUDS, on the other hand, are non-piped drainage systems (b) that minimise the impact of surface water runoff whilst also presenting an added value in so that they maximise the amenity and biodiversity opportunities of the environment they are applied to. [17] At the present, SUDS are not compulsory but the Regional Planning Bodies strongly promote the reliance on them. For instance, the Greater London Authority highlights the importance of using SUDS [17] in new developments wherever possible to ensure that surface water runoff is managed as close to its source as possible; and at the same time, GLA recognises the extra benefits offered by SUDS. [9] Among them one can list the fact that, by adding natural features to the urban environment, SUDS incorporate green infrastructures that enrich a citizen's experience of a city, which contribute to relax tired minds, counteract the stress created by city life and add monetary value to buildings. [13-16] In addition the contribution that SUDS make to reduce the risk of flooding is proactive, as opposed to reactive. On this basis, The Greater London Authority recommends that SUDS should be designed in ways that deliver other policy objectives of the GLA, such as water use efficiency and quality, biodiversity, amenity and recreation. [9]

Following to the information on pipe-based system and SUDS extracted from Butler and Davis [3], the table 1 below is presented to show a comparative analysis performed to establish SUDS's suitability to urban environments, capital cost, maintenance, land take, surface water runoff reduction and extra benefits (such as pollution reduction and amenity).

pervious surfaces. Yet, they carry with them extra benefits not only in terms of pollution reduction,⁷ but also in terms of biodiversity, wildlife, amenity, health, reduction of urban heat island effect. Related, green roofs increase the life of roofing materials, reduce the urban heat-island effect, [13] and reduce the energy demand.[9]

In sum, a number of different devices can be used to reduce surface water runoff and consequently the risk of surface water flooding in cities. However, their effectiveness, appropriateness, feasibility and sustainability vary greatly. Two of them in particular, as showed by the previous analysis, stand out and, when used in urban contexts, have clear advantages over the others: green roofs and pervious surfaces.

5. ADAPTATION STRATEGY WITHIN THE CITY BLOCK

5.1 Georgian block in Bloomsbury (London)

Bloomsbury can be succinctly categorised as a traditional development in London, one in which the mass of the city block defines streets and squares. [1] The application of the methodology provided in section 2, point (b) of this paper, results into an overall degree of impermeability of 0.8 of the chosen Georgian block case study. In order to mitigate the predicted amount of rainfall, which is expected to be higher in the forthcoming years, the overall degree of impermeability should be reduced to 0.6 (20% reduction corresponding to the 20% predicted increase in rainfall).

A possible strategy (A) that may be used to reach the required degree of impermeability in Bloomsbury consists in simply intervening on the city block's roofs, namely, modifying the existing pitched roofs into green roofs. This linear strategy, however, takes no account of the historical dimension of Bloomsbury. Going along this route, accordingly, would mean to radically change the identity of the city block. And this, apart from any other consideration, would not be allowed, since most areas in Bloomsbury are qualified as conservation areas and so cannot be transformed at will (see fig. 5-strategy A).

An alternative strategy (B), which enables us to reduce the degree of impermeability in the Bloomsbury block to 0.7 (i.e. just short of the required degree), consists in turning exclusively the flat roofs of the buildings (flat roofs that can be found on the extensions at the back of most building) into green roofs, whilst adding planted areas in the backyards (see fig. 5-strategy B). The main problem that this strategy faces is economic in nature. For, the proposed intervention would mean that the hotels located in Bloomsbury would see their (back) terraces—which are a source of income due to their attractiveness from the point of view of a guest—transformed in planting areas—which, instead, are of little or no interest from the point of view of a guest. The overall attractiveness of the area, linked to its historical character would, accordingly, be severely penalised.

What the suggested strategies show is that in a Georgian city block the possibilities to reduce surface water runoff through green roofs are in fact extremely limited. This also suggests that a more effective intervention would require one to intervene on the squares located in the area where the Georgian block sits. By transforming them (or part thereof) into more absorbing areas it should be possible to integrate the intervention on roofs—intervention that has been showed to have a necessarily limited efficacy—by so contributing to reach the required degree of impermeability. This way, it may be possible to overcome the structural inflexibility that characterises the Georgian city block.

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Pollution resulting from rising traffic level is already a growing health problem in London. On this issue see Roaf *et al.* [14].

FIGURE 5. Surface water runoff reduction simulation in Bloomsbury (London): sketch of Bloomsbury showing two different strategies. (author's own)

5.2 Modernist block in Bethnal Green (London)

In general, Modernist developments can be concisely presented as separated pavilions freestanding on a greenfield site. [1] The application of the methodology provided in section 2, point (b) of this paper, results into an overall degree of impermeability in the Modernist block in Bethnal Green is 0.6. In order to mitigate the predicted amount of rainfall, which is expected to be higher in the forthcoming years, the overall degree of impermeability should be reduced to 0.5 (20% reduction corresponding to the 20% predicted increase in rainfall).

The strategies that can be explored in order to achieve this extra result may consist in either intervening on roofs or modifying pavements and streets. The basic ideas here are respectively that of turning the existing roofs into green roofs (first option) or substituting private pavements and streets with permeable surfaces (second option). It seems that the transforming the existing roofs (first option) is the less invasive and more advisable option from a practical point of view (cf. fig. 6-strategy A). For, not only is such a modification far from excessively demanding but also it has the further advantages of both increasing the buildings thermal performance and promoting biodiversity. By contrast, substituting private streets and pavements with pervious surfaces (second option) requires a much more destructive intervention that comes with high embodied carbon and carries few, if any, benefits in terms of amenity and biodiversity of the block.

In this context it is important to add that the modernist block has a significant capacity of water runoff reduction. In fact, its degree of impermeability can be further reduced to a 0.3 degree of impermeability—this way halving the existing 0.6 degree of impermeability and reaching a 45% water runoff reduction (see fig. 6-strategy B)—without an excessively invasive intervention. This is a peculiarity of the Modernist city block and one that clearly sets it apart from other typologies of city blocks (inclusive the Georgian one analysed above, which, in comparison, is characterised by a higher rigidity). Hence, the Modernist city block constitutes a most adaptable environment.

To that extent, the Modernist block should be regarded as a resource for the city. For, if we take a city-wide perspective, the preceding remarks justify the claim that the Modernist blocks have the potential to compensate for other parts of the city the impermeability of which can be modified only with greater difficulty. For instance, in the cases under review, one may opt for the strategy of intervention on Bethnal Green specified in fig. 6 (strategy B), since this has the potential to compensate for the strategy B of intervention on Bloomsbury introduced in fig. 5.

FIGURE 6. Surface water runoff reduction simulation in Bethnal Green (London): sketch of Bethnal Green showing two different strategies. (author's own)

6. CONCLUSIONS

London may be affected by different kinds of flooding. However, not all of them have the same importance or can occur with the same likelihood. A central place is occupied by surface water flooding. Apart from constituting a specific kind of flooding it may be a consequence of other types of flooding having their primary sources elsewhere. In addition, the awareness of the mutual interrelations and the common causes of certain typologies of flooding can be used as an insightful starting point to criticise certain proposed strategies of intervention (such as the implementation of the Thames barrier) that are more concerned with effects as opposed to the real causes of flooding.

This is the reason why in this paper I have mainly focused on surface water runoff. In this context, I have identified and critically assessed a number of strategies and means that can be used to deal with excess of water runoff in London. In this part of my work I have noticed that only some systems used so far to control the surface water runoff in an urban environment are both effective in reducing the risk of flooding and suitable to the specific context, or city block, to which they are applied. In particular, I have criticised the proposal to simply update and enlarge the current capacity of the pipe-based drainage system in place in London. A far better strategy to deal with surface water runoff consists, I have argued, in reducing the amount of water entering municipal sewers. To achieve this objective, reliance on non-pipe based systems (SUDS) has been recognised as the most advisable strategy. SUDS have a twofold effect: for one thing, putting them in place immediately reduces the amount of water going through the traditional pipe-based systems; for another thing, SUDS secure a more efficient water use and, hence, add to the quality and biodiversity of the location where they are used. In this context, a comparative analysis has shown that green roofs and pervious surfaces are the most effective devices to reduce surface water runoff in London as well as the most suitable system within a city.

Building on this conclusion, I have subjected green roofs and pervious surfaces to an analytical critical treatment comprising both a quantitative simulation within the city block. With a view of making the simulation manageable I have focused on two specific areas in London: a typical Georgian block in Bloomsbury, and Modernist block in Bethnal Green. This treatment has enabled me to conclude that the resort to green roofs and pervious surface as devices to reduce surface water runoff produces diverse outcomes in different contexts. More specifically, I have shown that Bloomsbury is a less adaptable environment when compared to Bethnal Green. As a result, whereas adding green roofs in Bloomsbury (and, to generalise, in historical city blocks of the Bloomsbury type) can effectively mitigate the excess of surface water runoff, it does not fit well with the morphological characteristics of the area and so should be considered a sub-optimal solution. Therefore, the intervention required by the necessity to reduce the amount of surface water runoff need take place in this typology of city block through the introduction of new pervious surfaces. The same conclusion does not hold true for Bethnal Green (and, again to generalise, Modernist city blocks), which can be adapted to cope with surface water runoff by turning part of the existing covered roofs into green roofs. This solution is both effective and coherent with the morphological features of the Modernist city block. Furthermore, the Modernist city block can be made even less vulnerable to surface water runoff through the addition of permeable surfaces on the private streets and the introduction of planted areas in the open space, which is abundant, within the block. In a nutshell, the Modernist block is more adaptable than the traditional one, to the effect that it can meet more efficiently and easily some of the challenges associated with climate change.

Finally, it is worth to underline that the most relevant implication of this approach to adaptation, in the context of the present study, is that whereas surface water flooding tends to

occur in certain specific areas, it has to be dealt with on a wider and less local scale. That is, the 'active' catchments are not confined to a specific block but rather include the whole city. City blocks, in other words, should be regarded as cellular components of a whole landscape, of which they are part and parcel. This overall approach justifies the related claim that the study of the fundamental features of each city block can shed light on a city's potential and suitability to be adapted in order to reduce its vulnerability to surface water runoff. This will also give important indications on how proficient certain devices are in reducing the risk of surface water runoff when those devices are contextualised in, and applied to, a given area of the city.

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REFERENCES

1. Baxter, A., *London's Natural Signature* (2011), available from: <http://www.naturalengland.org.uk/regions/london/ourwork/wildlondon/naturalsignatures/default.aspx> [last accessed: Dec 2011].
2. Bibby, P.R. & J.W. Shepherd (1997) *Projecting Rates of Urbanisation in England, 1991-2016: Method, Policy Application and Results*. *Town Planning Review*, 68(1), 93-124.
3. Butler D. & J. Davis, *Urban Drainage*. London: E&FN Spon (2011).
4. Environment Agency, *Thames Catchment Flood Management Plan* (2009), available from: <http://cdn.environment-agency.gov.uk/geth1209bqyl-e-e.pdf> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
5. Great Britain, *The Flood and Water Management Act* (2010), available from: http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/29/pdfs/ukpga_20100029_en.pdf [last accessed: Nov 2011].
6. Great Britain. Mayor of London, *London Regional Flood Risk Appraisal* (2009), available from: <http://legacy.london.gov.uk/mayor/strategies/sds/docs/regional-flood-risk09.pdf> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
7. Great Britain. Office of the Deputy Prime Minister *Preparing for Flood* (2003), available from <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/uploads/odpm/4000000009282.pdf> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
8. Greater London Authority (2011a). *Managing Risks and Increasing Resilience*, available from: <http://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Adaptation-oct11.pdf> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
9. Greater London Authority (2011b). *The London Plan*, available from: <http://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/The%20London%20Plan%202011.pdf> [last accessed: Nov 2011].

10. Habraken, J., *Structure of the Ordinary: Form and Control in the Built Environment*. Cambridge (Mass): MIT Press (2000).
11. Jarman, M., *Climate Change*. London: Pluto (2007).
12. Panerai et al., *Urban forms: Death and Life of the Urban Block*. Boston: Architectural Press (2004).
13. Ritchie, A. & R. Thomas, *Sustainable Urban Design: an Environmental Approach* (2nd ed.). London: Taylor & Francis (2009).
14. Roaf, S. D. Chricton & N. Nicol, *Adapting Buildings and Cities for Climate Change. A 21st Century Survival guide* (2nd. Ed.). Oxford: Elsevier (2009).
15. Shaw, R., M. Colley, & R. Connell, *Climate Change Adaptation by Design: A Guide for Sustainable Communities* (2007), available from: http://www.tcpa.org.uk/data/files/bd_cca.pdf [last accessed: Nov 2011].
16. Viljoen, A., *Continuous Productive Urban Landscapes: Designing Urban Agriculture for Sustainable Cities*. London: Architectural Press (2005).
17. Woods-Ballard B. et al., *The SUDS Manual*. London: CIRIA (2007).
18. Environmental Agency – *Flooding from Surface Water*, available from: <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/research/planning/109490.aspx> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
19. Environmental Agency – *Sources of Flooding*, available from: <http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/homeandleisure/floods/31652.aspx> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
20. Greater London Authority – *Drain London*, available from: <http://www.london.gov.uk/drain-london> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
21. UK Climate Projections. *London Map: Change in Winter Precipitations*, available from: <http://ukclimateprojections.defra.gov.uk/content/view/1417/499/> [last accessed: Nov 2011].
22. UK Climate Projections – *Key Findings for London 2080s*, available from: <http://ukclimateprojections.defra.gov.uk/content/view/2202/499/> [last accessed: Nov 2011].